

Effect of introducing σ^2, λ^3 -phosphorus in indolizine nucleus : a theoretical study[†]

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Ab initio quantum chemical calculations of the indolizine, aza-, diaza- and triazaindolizines and their various possible mono phospho-analogues obtained by replacement of one =CH- in the five membered ring by sp^2 -phosphorus (in all 20 systems : A-T) have been carried out at the B3LYP/6-311G** hybrid density functional level of theory. Thus different parameters of the molecular geometries and electronic structures, namely bond lengths, bond angles, total atomic charges, total energies, dipole moments and energies of the frontier molecular orbitals have been determined for these systems. σ^2, λ^3 -Phosphorus is found to be well integrated with the aromatic system which is further supported by NBO calculations of A-C. Although introduction of the σ^2, λ^3 -phosphorus in the five membered ring causes perceptible changes in the geometrical and electronic parameters, the aromatic character is comparable with that of the indolizine.

Introduction

Azaphospholes¹⁻³ may be conceived as derived from the classical azoles such as pyrrole, pyrazole, imidazole, etc. by replacing one ring =CH- by an sp^2 -phosphorus atom (=P-). The two-coordinate trivalent phosphorus contributes one π -electron only to the aromatic sextet which is completed by the contribution of two electrons by the nitrogen.

The diagonal relationship between the elements in the periodic table is well documented but its existence in the carbon-phosphorus pair has been realized only lately⁴⁻⁶. The $>C=P$ -^{7,8} and $-C\equiv P$ ⁹ functionalities participate in the pericyclic reactions as effectively as $>C=C<$ and $-C\equiv C-$ moieties. The resemblance between heterophospholes and heteroles has been found so remarkable that the former have been termed as a postscript chapter of the heterocyclic chemistry¹⁰. The analogies between the syntheses and reactions of the anellated heterophospholes and their non-phosphorus analogues have been highlighted recently¹¹. During the last few years we have extended successfully the synthetic methods reported for the classical heterocycles to their phosphorus containing analogues. Thus by [4+1] cyclocondensation of 1,2-dialkylpyridinium halides with phosphorus trichloride in presence of triethylamine we could obtain 1,3-azaphospholo[1,5-*a*]pyridines which were named as 2-phosphaindolizines¹²⁻¹⁴ in view of the presence of a σ^2, λ^3 -phosphorus in the 2-position of the indolizine nucleus. The isomeric 1-phosphaindolizine was reported by Märkl

and coworkers¹⁵. 1- and 2-Phosphaindolizines were prepared by Regitz and coworkers also from [3+2]cycloaddition reaction¹⁶. 3-Phosphaindolizine has not been prepared as yet. Following the [4+1]cyclocondensation strategy we subsequently obtained 1-aza-2-phosphaindolizines¹⁷, 3-aza-2-phosphaindolizines¹⁸, 1,3-diaza-2-phosphaindolizines¹⁹ besides some other heterocycles having 1,3-azaphosphole ring anellated with the thiazole²⁰, oxazole²¹ or benzo-thiazole²⁰ nucleus. 1-Aza-2-phosphaindolizines could be prepared through an alternative [3+2]cyclocondensation route²². Recently we extended another strategy, namely 1,5-electrocyclization, reported for indolizines and other heterocycles²³, to the synthesis of 2-phosphaindolizines^{24,25} and 1,3-azaphospholo[5,1-*a*]isoquinolines²⁶. As a result of these successful preparations we could establish unequivocally that a close analogy exists between the synthetic methods of indolizines and their phospho-analogues²⁷.

In contrast to indolizines²⁸, the regioselective bromination of 2-phosphaindolizines²⁹ in 1-position could be correlated with the π -charge densities in the two systems obtained by semiempirical MNDO calculations¹². Likewise, the successful Diels-Alder reactions of 1,3-azaphospholo[5,1-*a*]isoquinolines and [1,5-*a*]pyridines are explainable on the basis of the frontier orbital energies obtained from semiempirical PM3 calculations^{26,30}. PM3 optimized geometries of 1- and 2-phosphaindolizines have been compared with their X-ray structures¹⁴. *Ab initio* calculations of monocyclic and benzo-anellated azaphospholes have been

[†]Dedicated to Professor S. M. Mukherji.

Fig. 1. B3LYP/6-311G** Optimized geometries of indolizines and phosphaindolizines with their IUPAC and common (in parenthesis) names.

carried out to determine the extent of aromaticity^{31–33}. These results prompted us to investigate the analogies between indolizines including aza and diazaindolizines and their different possible pyrido-anellated phospho-analogues by computational methods and the results are presented here.

Calculations :

Computational calculations were carried out using the Gaussian 98 program³⁴. The geometries of all 20 systems (A–T) were fully optimized in the ground state, without any geometrical constraints, initially at PM3 and finally at the restricted Becke's three-parameter hybrid functional in conjunction with the correlation functional of Lee, Yang and Parr (B3LYP) level with 6-311G(d,p) basis set and (5D,7F) functions. Vibrational frequencies were also calculated at the same level and the zero NIMAG (number of imaginary frequencies) values confirmed the optimized geometries to be the real minima on the potential energy surface. Stabilization energies from π bonding-antibonding interactions have been calculated at the same level by using NBO program³⁵ as implemented in Gaussian 98 package.

Optimized molecular structures have been drawn with the help of Gauss View 2.1³⁶ software.

Results and discussion

The optimized molecular geometries of these 20 pyrido-anellated heterocyclic systems (A–T) along with their IUPAC and common names are shown in Fig. 1. The B3LYP/6-311G** calculated bond lengths, bond angles and dihedral angles of the five membered ring are given in Table 1.

The geometries of the anellated ring systems A–T are found to be nearly planar, ω_{2348a} and ω_{218a4} being $\sim 0^\circ$ (0.0 ± 0.020) which is in accordance with the aromatic stabilization. The CH/P exchange does not alter the C–C and C–N bond lengths significantly. The P–C bond lengths between 172.6–176.8 pm (as compared to 173.3 pm for phosphabenzene³⁷) and P–N bond lengths between 166.2–170.5 pm tend toward equalization indicating significant delocalization of the π -electrons. The values are between those for covalent single and double bond lengths (P–C 187; P=C 166; P–N 180; P=N 160 pm) in agreement with the

Table 1. Selected B3LYP/6-311G** calculated bond lengths, bond angles and dihedral angles of indolizines and phosphaindolizines

System	Bond lengths (pm)					Bond angles ($^\circ$)					Dihedral angles ($^\circ$)	
	a	b	c	d	e	α	β	γ	δ	ϵ	ω_{218a4}	ω_{2348a}
A	139.2	140.9	138.3	137.0	141.0	107.3	108.6	107.9	109.1	107.1	0.000	0.000
B	176.3	176.9	136.8	137.8	140.4	89.3	113.6	112.9	113.0	112.2	0.001	0.001
C	138.5	175.6	173.1	137.0	141.2	112.7	89.5	113.3	113.1	111.4	0.000	0.000
D	139.9	139.0	173.8	175.9	139.8	112.4	114.1	89.4	113.7	111.4	0.000	0.000
E	132.7	136.2	137.8	137.8	141.0	105.3	112.2	105.3	106.3	110.9	0.000	0.000
F	131.4	169.4	172.6	137.4	141.9	111.4	92.7	109.9	110.8	115.1	0.000	0.000
G	133.4	133.9	174.0	176.0	139.7	109.9	117.6	85.9	111.4	115.2	0.000	0.000
H	138.8	136.1	131.8	137.1	141.2	110.6	106.8	111.5	106.5	104.6	0.000	0.000
I	176.0	170.1	129.5	138.4	140.2	91.1	112.5	116.4	111.2	108.9	0.000	0.000
J	140.5	133.2	164.1	176.8	139.6	115.1	113.8	91.4	109.9	109.6	0.000	0.000
K	139.5	140.0	133.9	134.9	139.8	104.8	113.3	104.0	112.7	105.1	0.000	0.000
L	176.5	176.7	132.1	135.2	139.2	86.0	118.5	108.4	116.8	110.7	0.000	0.000
M	139.2	174.1	166.9	133.7	140.2	109.4	93.6	110.1	116.9	109.9	0.019	0.020
N	132.4	136.5	131.2	137.3	140.0	107.2	111.6	110.2	103.8	109.8	-0.001	-0.011
O	133.9	133.1	164.6	175.8	139.1	111.4	116.2	89.9	108.0	114.6	0.005	0.000
P	133.4	134.9	133.2	135.5	139.3	102.9	116.8	101.7	109.9	108.8	0.007	-0.019
Q	132.3	168.6	166.2	134.3	141.1	108.5	96.8	107.0	114.5	113.2	0.002	-0.001
R	139.2	138.8	130.8	135.8	138.7	108.9	110.7	106.5	111.1	102.8	0.001	0.000
S	176.2	170.5	127.7	138.2	138.3	89.8	117.2	110.5	115.5	107.8	0.004	0.025
T	133.2	134.3	129.8	135.8	137.6	105.8	112.9	105.4	108.2	107.5	0.002	0.000

earlier results³¹⁻³³ though in the case of 2-aza-3-phospha derivatives (**J/O**), the P-N₄ bond length becomes comparatively longer (175.8/176.2 pm) at the cost of P-N₂ bond length (164.1/164.6 pm) probably due to repulsion between lone pair on phosphorus and orthogonal electron pair on N₄. But in **Q**, the balancing effect of the two nitrogen lone pairs on both sides of phosphorus makes P-N₁ (168.6 pm) and P-N₃ (166.2 pm) bond lengths almost equal which supports increased delocalization. The bond angle at P lies in the range 86–97° regardless of its position in the five-membered ring and is in agreement with the reported values³. Increase in the number of vicinal nitrogen atoms increases its value expectedly.

Total atomic charge on different ring atoms are presented in Table 2. The CH/P exchange in the five membered ring at 1-position causes small negative charge (–0.005 – –0.078) on otherwise positive (0.168–0.450) C_{8a} and a decrease in the net negative charge on N₄ atom, but in the 3-phospha derivatives there is considerable increase in the net negative charge on N₄.

Calculated physical data viz. total energy, zero point correction, thermal energy, dipole moment and energy levels of frontier molecular orbitals are given in Table 3. Total energy of the system decreases progressively with the increase in the number of N or P atoms in the five membered ring. Among the three isomeric phosphaindolizines (**B-D**), 1- and 3-phospha isomers are more stable than the 2-phospha isomer by 1.13 and 7.47 kcal/mol respectively. Likewise, **L** (1-phospha isomer) is more stable than its 2-phospha isomer **M** by 2.51 kcal/mol and **G** (3-phospha isomer) is more stable than its 2-phospha isomer **F** by 5.33 kcal/mol. As a general trend, the dipole moment of the molecule increases with the increase in the number of heteroatoms in the five membered ring, while among the isomers having the same number of heteroatoms, dipole moment of the molecule having the nitrogen at 2-position is higher than that having phosphorus at the 2-position. It can be noted that the CH/P exchange causes the lowering of the frontier molecular orbital energies. It has been established earlier that in cycloaditions it is the LUMO of the C=P bond which participates in the interactions. Thus lowering of the LUMO of 2-

Table 2. Total atomic charge (Mulliken) at ring atoms of indolizines and phosphaindolizines

System	Ring position								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	8a
A	-0.153	-0.165	0.047	-0.403	0.168	-0.240	-0.010	-0.158	0.233
B	0.299	-0.460	0.118	-0.360	0.168	-0.239	0.011	-0.174	-0.032
C	-0.480	0.357	-0.252	-0.377	0.160	-0.232	-0.003	-0.160	0.326
D	-0.153	-0.357	0.368	-0.653	0.195	-0.229	0.002	-0.154	0.334
E	-0.332	-0.053	-0.007	-0.383	0.172	-0.246	0.004	-0.175	0.372
F	-0.575	0.429	-0.278	-0.367	0.171	-0.238	0.009	-0.162	0.432
G	-0.306	-0.261	0.352	-0.638	0.197	-0.231	0.007	-0.162	0.450
H	-0.045	-0.287	0.144	-0.390	0.163	-0.232	-0.007	-0.158	0.168
I	0.375	-0.503	0.224	-0.366	0.177	-0.238	0.107	-0.185	-0.078
J	0.154	-0.480	0.465	-0.633	0.221	-0.036	-0.002	-0.114	0.316
K	-0.315	0.093	-0.216	-0.332	0.194	-0.240	-0.002	-0.182	0.356
L	0.271	-0.230	-0.159	-0.274	0.204	-0.236	0.014	-0.186	-0.005
M	-0.510	0.485	-0.395	-0.319	0.197	-0.234	0.006	-0.182	0.374
N	-0.254	-0.200	0.138	-0.403	0.173	-0.236	0.002	-0.148	0.335
O	-0.223	-0.364	0.487	-0.646	0.191	-0.227	0.008	-0.148	0.434
P	-0.345	0.099	-0.203	-0.313	0.206	-0.245	0.007	-0.192	0.394
Q	-0.579	0.529	-0.389	-0.316	0.206	-0.239	0.012	-0.174	0.460
R	-0.014	-0.189	-0.070	-0.338	0.205	-0.238	0.004	-0.169	0.222
S	0.393	-0.354	-0.019	-0.310	0.215	-0.238	0.021	-0.186	-0.019
T	-0.275	-0.077	-0.055	-0.369	0.209	-0.238	0.008	-0.164	0.446

Table 3. B3LYP/6-311G** calculated physical data of indolizines and phosphaindolizines (A-T)

System	Total energy (a.u.) E(RB + HF-LYP)	Relative energy (a.u.)	Zero-point correction (kcal/mol)	Thermal energy (kcal/mol)	Dipole moment (Debye)	HOMO (eV)	LUMO (eV)
A	-363.8890	0.0	80.80	84.68	1.1550	-5.22	-0.82
B	-666.5495	-302.6605	71.23	75.35	3.3801	-5.33	-1.29
C	-666.5473	-302.6583	71.12	75.23	3.0275	-5.71	-1.37
D	-666.5614	-302.6724	71.12	75.25	2.1330	-5.29	-1.26
E	-379.9420	0.0	73.71	77.45	3.3129	-5.92	-1.14
F	-682.6038	-302.6618	63.80	67.79	4.3876	-6.28	-1.64
G	-682.6123	-302.6703	64.02	68.00	2.9089	-5.88	-1.51
H	-379.9355	0.0	73.65	77.42	3.3655	-5.58	-1.23
I	-682.6006	-302.6651	63.88	67.91	4.9480	-5.60	-1.68
J	-682.6116	-302.6761	63.80	67.83	4.2647	-5.53	-1.49
K	-379.9259	0.0	73.77	77.49	2.1115	-5.85	-1.12
L	-682.5824	-302.6565	64.05	68.02	2.9683	-5.82	-1.65
M	-682.5782	-302.6523	63.74	67.71	3.6202	-6.33	-1.61
N	-395.9627	0.0	66.15	69.82	5.6830	-6.42	-1.65
O	-698.6312	-302.6496	56.21	60.14	5.6666	-6.29	-1.78
P	-395.9816	0.0	66.67	70.26	3.1175	-6.65	-1.46
Q	-698.6433	-302.6617	56.52	60.36	3.8869	-6.91	-1.89
R	-395.9484	0.0	66.06	69.71	4.7927	-6.30	-1.58
S	-698.6062	-302.6578	56.05	59.99	5.4290	-6.17	-1.94
T	-411.9808	0.0	58.59	62.15	6.1898	-7.14	-2.01

phosphaindolizine is expected to favour the [2+3] and [2+4] cycloadditions. This is in accordance with the finding that introduction of phosphorus in the diene or dienophile causes the lowering of the energy of activation of the Diels-Alder reaction^{38,39}.

In order to determine the effect of CH/P exchange on aromatic stabilization, Natural Bond Orbital Analysis of indolizine (A) and its 1- and 2-phospha analogues (B and C) has been done. Some important calculated stabilization energies ΔE_{ij} associated with donor-acceptor NBO $i \rightarrow j$, estimated from donor orbital occupancy and donor acceptor orbital energies, are given in Table 4, which indicate that the stabilization due to delocalization of π -electrons in B and C is comparable with that in A. The $\pi_{5,6} \rightarrow n_4$ interaction between the nitrogen lone pair and π orbital of C₅-C₆ gives strongest stabilization in each case which is 52.65 and 45.81 kcal/mol more in the case of B and C as compared to that in A. Other significant interactions are due to delocalization of the nitrogen lone pair into the vicinal antibonding orbitals $\pi_{1,8a}^*$, $\pi_{2,3}^*$ and $\pi_{5,6}^*$. Due to these delocalizations, the highest energy (-0.26076 a.u.) NBO in A is nitrogen lone pair with lowest occupancy (1.49393 electrons). In case of B and C, the occupancy is even lower

{1.47797 electrons (-0.27670 a.u.) and 1.47442 electrons (-0.27567 a.u.) respectively} indicating more effective delocalization of nitrogen lone pair. Second highest NBO in B and C is the phosphorus lone pair with higher occupancy (1.97334 and 1.97710 electrons respectively) indicating its intactness.

Table 4. Stabilization energies E_{ij} (kcal/mol) from bond-antibond interactions in A, B and C as obtained from NBO calculations

NBO Interaction ($i \rightarrow j$)	A	B	C
$\pi_{1,2} \rightarrow \pi_{8,8a}^*$	6.60	5.20	7.38
$\pi_{1,8a} \rightarrow \pi_{2,3}^*$	23.57	16.75	12.31
$\pi_{1,8a} \rightarrow \pi_{7,8}^*$	18.61	21.08	15.83
$\pi_{2,3} \rightarrow \pi_{1,8a}^*$	15.94	7.26	11.26
$n_4 \rightarrow \pi_{1,8a}^*$	31.68	41.82	35.17
$n_4 \rightarrow \pi_{2,3}^*$	31.25	33.25	37.36
$n_4 \rightarrow \pi_{5,6}^*$	35.07	33.11	32.29
$\pi_{5,6} \rightarrow n_4$	189.58	242.23	235.39
$\pi_{5,6} \rightarrow \pi_{7,8}^*$	14.72	14.60	14.62
$\pi_{7,8} \rightarrow \pi_{1,8a}^*$	18.65	20.68	19.75
$\pi_{7,8} \rightarrow \pi_{5,6}^*$	16.91	17.81	16.85

Conclusions :

The CH/P exchange in the indolizine and its aza- and diaza-analogues does not cause appreciable deviations in the C–C and C–N bond lengths indicating comparable π -delocalizations which is further supported by the P–C and P–N bond lengths being between isolated single and double bond lengths. The total energies of phosphaindolizines are much lower than those of their non-phosphorus analogues. NBO results also support the presence of conjugated system, hence, high degree of aromatic character in these compounds. The CH/P exchange causes lowering of the frontier molecular orbital energies thereby making these compounds more reactive towards [2+3] and [2+4]cycloadditions.

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Gupta *et al.* : Effect of introducing σ^2, λ^3 -phosphorus in indolizine nucleus : a theoretical study

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